

Automatic shadow detection in high-resolution optical satellite imagery

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This paper presents a principled approach for detecting shadows in satellite imagery at a large scale. We propose a two-stage process, starting with the generation of a training set based on an airborne LiDAR point cloud and a target satellite image. This point cloud is first rasterised onto the spatial grid of the image (0.5m). Shadows are then geometrically projected using a standard hillshade algorithm. Finally we improve the quality of the training set by handling small objects and removing "bright" shadows that appear due to temporal misalignment between image and point cloud. The second stage leverages Deep Learning (DL) to automatically detect shadows in areas where airborne LiDAR is not available, or out of date. Our experiments on manually labeled shadows demonstrate that introducing variance to solar azimuth helps to reduce confusions with water and dark surfaces (asphalt). We further show that the learned model is able to replicate the quality of the LiDAR-based shadow maps on small and medium-sized shadows, in a geographical area unseen during training. We believe increasing the size of the training data set to more diverse cities would improve generalization on large shadows and on vegetation.

1 Introduction

Shadows appear in satellite imagery due to the presence of high vertical structures and can often be found in urban areas [1–3]. Accurately localizing shadows is essential for many downstream applications, described in the following paragraphs.

In Land Use / Land Cover classification [4–9], shadows are problematic because their radiometry is similar to water and dark surfaces (wet asphalt). Shadow removal [10, 11] requires a high recall shadow map to avoid information loss in illuminated areas of the scene.

High resolution shadow maps are also useful in the context of 3D reconstruction. Shadows contain valuable information about the height of nearby vertical structures, previous works have proposed to extract al-

titude or semantic information from images based on shadow maps [12–16]. Moreover, shadows are often problematic for correlation-based stereo-vision methods [17–21], as they are by nature areas with high ambiguity [22, 23], and therefore can cause either outliers [24] or holes [25] in the 3D representation. Emerging DL pipelines that aim to detect surface elevation based on either single view estimation [26] or implicit representation learning (Neural Radiance Fields) [27–29] may also benefit from shadow detection as an annex task to 3D reconstruction.

Recently, DL models have been applied to automatically detect shadows in Aerial imagery [30–33]. Our approach extends the concept of [30] to satellite imagery, by introducing 3 contributions which are detailed in the following sections.

First, in Section 2.1 we show how the costly manual annotation process required for large vision models [32, 33] can, to a certain extent, be replaced by an automatic shadow mask production pipeline based on 3D point cloud data. We then demonstrate a rasterisation process that filters out high voltage lines, and propose a post-processing scheme to create a training dataset with sufficient quality for the DL model.

In Section 2.2 we describe our DL pipeline and the architecture of the Convolutional Neural Network. We show how a single rotation augmentation of the value of the solar azimuth is sufficient to introduce a task-specific variance and to improve detection accuracy.

We evaluate the quality of both the automatic shadow mask production and the DL inference on a manually labeled dataset of $5km^2$ in Montpellier, France, described in Section 3.1, held out from training. Finally we demonstrate the results of training on cities in France and running inference on Ankara, Turkey, an area which is unseen during training and for which no 3D point cloud is available. The entire dataset (manual and automatic) as well as the code will be made public to ensure reproducible work.

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2 Methodology

2.1 Automatic shadow mask production pipeline

The following paragraphs describe the 6 main steps of the pipeline.

Figure 1: Automatic shadow mask production pipeline scheme

Rasterisation : The first module projects the 3D point cloud onto a grid of cells aligned with the orthorectified satellite image pixels. Its effectiveness depends on how the points are aggregated for each cell. For most surfaces, we find that taking the maximum altitude produces visually satisfactory shadows, as shown in Figure 3a. However, it may fall short when dealing with cells that contain multiple objects at different altitudes. The presence of high voltage lines leads to incorrect shadows. To address this issue, we propose to use the median instead of the maximum. Figure 3b shows that the median rasterisation significantly reduces incorrect shadows. However, applying median value everywhere compromises the accuracy of the shadow contours (Red circles in Figure 3b). Therefore we only use the median value within a margin of several meters on either side of the high voltage line, obtained from a publicly available source [34]. This module offers the flexibility to apply an alternative rasterisation method on designated areas via a mask.

Nodata Filling : The second module is designed to fill in the gaps in the Digital Surface Model (DSM) raster which can be incomplete due to the lack of points in certain grid cells. We have opted to take the local minimum within a defined radius, which proved to be more coherent in our case than the commonly used "Inverse Distance Weighting" (IDW) method.

Shadow Extraction : The method used to produce the shadow mask is a standard hillshade algorithm based on ray tracing. Issues on objects with significant

vertical overhang remain relatively rare in the dataset, but could be an issue in other areas.

Morphological operations : The raw shadow mask produced contains noise, holes, and lacks regularity in shadow shapes (shown in Figure 3c). Several morphological operations such as erosion, dilation, removal of small objects, and hole filling were tested. The removal of small objects and hole filling were retained as they produced the highest accuracy masks relative to the manually labeled shadows (See Table 1).

Bright Areas Suppression : Changes in the scene that occur between the date of the LiDAR measurement and the satellite image can cause erroneous shadows, shown in Figure 2. To remove these false shadows, we design a module called "Bright Areas Suppression" (BAS) which computes the mean color of each connected component of the shadow mask. If this mean exceeds a threshold (set relatively high at a value of 150 on an 8-bit scale), the shadow is removed from the dataset.

Figure 2: Example of bright areas suppression (Green : areas suppressed by BAS; Blue : areas untouched by BAS)

GrabCut : The last module applies the GrabCut algorithm [35], commonly used for object extraction from a background, to refine the edges of the shadow mask. GrabCut requires an initial mask composed of four classes: "foreground" pixels that remain after a single erosion, "probably foreground" and "probably background" pixels extracted from the difference between the mask and its respectively eroded and dilated version, "background" for the remaining pixels. Table 1 shows the effectiveness of this final post-processing step.

2.2 Deep Learning method

We have chosen "ResUnet" as backbone architecture for our learning model using size and shape hyper-parameters from [36]. Our initial experiments, explained in section 3.2.2, show that this architecture performs as well as more complex solutions like

(a) Rasterisation step : Max (b) Rasterisation step : Median

(c) Comparison before/after shadow mask refinement (Red : pixels suppressed by mask refinement modules; Green : Shadow mask at the end of the pipeline)

Figure 3: Key steps of the pipeline

atrous convolutions or attention modules. One improvement we are able to demonstrate is the introduction of variance to the solar angle. We rotate the images in the training dataset by the value of the solar azimuth. This operation is also done at inference time. The goal of this step is to encourage the network to learn the causality of geometric shadow formation, as well as direction-specific convolutional filters.

3 Results

3.1 Experimental setup

Images : We conducted tests on four satellite images of the urban areas of : Montpellier (France, 12/09/2019), Nice (France, 30/08/2020), Amsterdam (the Netherlands, 24/04/2022) and Ankara (Turkey, 13/10/2022). The Montpellier and Nice images are derived from Pléiades HR products [37] obtained and refined from Airbus Defense and Space (ADS). Amsterdam and Ankara products were processed by the CNES Pleiades World Heritage (PWH) pipeline. All of the images were pan-sharpened with the ORFEO Tool-Box Library [38] and orthorectified with an internal library. They were rotated by the sun azimuth angle, as explained in Figure 4, producing horizontal rays with the sun on the left.

Figure 4: Scheme of azimuth rotation applied to images viewed from a nadir angle

Point clouds : Groundtruth LiDAR point clouds on France and the Netherlands were respectively obtained from IGN (National Institute of Geographic and Forest Information) [39] and AHN (Actueel Hoogtebestand Nederland, the Current Dutch Elevation map) [40].

Manually labelled ground truth : A manual database of $5km^2$ on Montpellier was produced by labeling operators. The instructions were to ignore the shadows of transient objects (trucks, cars), to ignore the shadows of negligible size (smaller than 5-7 pixels), to focus on cast shadows of exploitable size, and to minimize confusion with water and wet asphalt. Three types of urban morphology were selected : peri-urban, downtown, and industrial.

Model training : In terms of learning hyper-parameters, we used patches of 256×256 pixels with a batch size ranging from 8 to 10. Training was conducted for 50 epochs using Adam optimizer and a reduce-on-plateau scheduler. The learning rate was set to 0.01 with a binary cross-entropy loss. The metrics used to analyse training and results are : Accuracy, Precision, Recall and F1 score.

3.2 Analysis

3.2.1 Automatic pipeline evaluation

Quantitative evaluations of the automatically generated training data with respect to the manual one was

Step \ Metrics	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
Hillshade	0.859	0.455	0.896	0.604
Morphology	0.870	0.478	0.900	0.624
BAS	0.877	0.492	0.898	0.636
GrabCut	0.905	0.563	0.924	0.699

Table 1: Evolution of metrics throughout pipeline steps (BAS = Bright Areas Suppression)

conducted to ensure the effectiveness of each individual pipeline processing modules. As shown in Table 1, every mask refinement module improves all of the performance metrics.

3.2.2 Deep Learning method evaluation

Comparison with threshold method : Threshold methods [41] are considered classical approaches for shadow detection. We manually tuned a threshold-per-band method and provide a "low" and a "high" blue-band threshold versions. We compare our network’s predictions over two Montpellier complementary evaluation sets : the automatically-produced ("auto") set excluding the manually labelled zone, and the manual set. The comparison to our network’s predictions in Table 2 demonstrate the superiority of DL approach over thresholding. The latter involves a trade-off between precision and recall: a higher threshold on the blue band allows to retrieve more shadows but increase false detections, especially on water areas. When removing the latters from the evaluation sets, precision reaches for respectively the "high" and "low" threshold methods 0.864 and 0.891 on the auto set, and 0.903 and 0.930 on the manual set, while DL methods maintain their performances.

Eval Set	Method	Precision	Recall	F1 score
Auto	Threshold "High"	0.267	0.165	0.204
Auto	Threshold "Low"	0.366	0.152	0.215
Auto	DL trained on Nice	0.762	0.473	0.584
Manual	Threshold "High"	0.792	0.667	0.724
Manual	Threshold "Low"	0.813	0.589	0.680
Manual	DL Nice	0.664	0.800	0.725
Manual	DL Nice, Montpellier	0.657	0.935	0.771

Table 2: Comparison between Threshold and DL methods with automatic and manual datasets

Comparison with Machine Learning and Deep Learning methods : In addition to threshold methods, we have compared our results to other ML and DL methods, respectively a Random Forest (RF) [42], AFFPNet [43], SwinUnet [44], and ResUnet++ [45]. These methods are trained and evaluated on the Montpellier dataset.

The features used for the RF are computed for each image band and are composed of the pixel value, the x and y sobel gradients, and five characteristics derived from the gray level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM). The GLCM features capture textural information, providing a richer set of data for the model. These features complement pixel intensity and gradient information,

(a) City area

(b) Complex area

Figure 5: Difference map between predictions and manual ground truth on Montpellier for thresholding (top left), RF (top right), ResUnet (bottom left) and ResUnet++ (bottom right). Green = predicted but not in groundtruth (false positive), Red = In groundtruth but not predicted (false negative), rightly predicted pixels (true and false positives) are transparent.

enhancing the model’s ability to distinguish different classes. This robustness to variations in illumination and contrast is particularly beneficial for accurately segmenting complex regions like shadows.

Quantitative results gathered in Table 3 show that DL methods outperform both thresholding and RF. RF tends to over-segment shadows, whereas thresholding fails at recovering all the shadowed pixels. The four networks exhibit similar scores, albeit ResUnet scores being a little higher on the automatic dataset. Thus, additional modules like attention or atrous convolutions do not seem to help refine predictions. Since scores were computed from a single network training process, conclusions on networks relative performances should be nuanced.

These trends are confirmed by qualitative observations in common city areas (Figure 5a) and complex areas (Figure 5b). Even though non-deep learning meth-

ods work well on classic urban areas, they have difficulty segmenting shadows when there is water. In contrast, DL methods manage to handle this challenge effectively. No specific difference of behaviour was observed between the four network predictions.

Therefore, we decided to use ResUnet for our experiments as it provided the best compromise between efficiency (data frugality, training time, computing resources) and performances.

Eval Set	Method	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score
Auto restrained	Threshold	0.870	0.831	0.425	0.563
Auto restrained	Random Forest	0.855	0.594	0.834	0.694
Auto restrained	ResUnet	0.941	0.896	0.789	0.839
Auto restrained	ResUnet++	0.932	0.875	0.766	0.817
Auto restrained	AFFPNet	0.932	0.861	0.779	0.818
Auto restrained	SwinUnet	0.928	0.870	0.745	0.803
Manual	Threshold	0.939	0.792	0.667	0.724
Manual	Random Forest	0.831	0.410	0.948	0.573
Manual	ResUnet	0.933	0.652	0.944	0.771
Manual	ResUnet++	0.934	0.656	0.945	0.774
Manual	AFFPNet	0.930	0.638	0.950	0.763
Manual	SwinUnet	0.935	0.663	0.949	0.775

Table 3: Comparison between Threshold, Random Forest and four DL state-of-the-art networks with automatic (restrained to the manually labeled area) and manual datasets

Variance to solar angle : Making the network variant to the solar angle reveals to be beneficial. Table 4 shows that introducing a task-specific variance allows us to gain almost 3% improvement in F1-score compared to random rotations and flips in all directions. Flips maintain a unique solar direction in the training set. Surprisingly, it is the double flip combining left/right and up/down flips which performs best suggesting the network makes use of the solar direction (horizontal) but not its orientation (rays propagating from left to right). We think results could be enhanced by improving that correlation.

Augment.	None	All	Left/right Flip	Up/down Flip	Double flip
F1 score	0.729	0.733	0.738	0.749	0.758

Table 4: Impacts of data augmentation on F1 score (All = Random rotation + Left/right flip + Up/down flip)

Inferences : As shown in Figure 6a, the network generally predicts very well, both in areas with an urban morphology similar to the training area (Montpellier), and in test areas totally unseen during training. However, Figure 6b highlights that the network is unable to properly detect large shadows, which might be improved by adding cities with tall buildings in the dataset or increasing the network’s receptive field.

(a) Reliable inference on different areas (Top images taken in "Montpellier" area; Bottom images taken in "Ankara" area)

(b) Issue with prediction on large shadow

Figure 6: Results of networks’ inferences in heterogeneous and insightful areas (predicted shadows in red)

4 Discussion

We presented a two-stage pipeline for automatically detecting shadows in satellite imagery. Our pipeline projects shadows from LiDAR point clouds onto a satellite image. This is combined with pre and post-processing steps to improve quality. We then demonstrated that this automatically produced dataset was sufficiently accurate to serve as training data for a DL algorithm, using manual labels. Our experiments show that decent generalization performance is achieved, although some limitations remain.

Overall, vegetation seems to be overdetected in the training dataset production stage, which could be improved by using semantic information in the point cloud. Another interesting approach would be to try to correct the errors that remain using the trained DL model.

In the inference results, small and medium shadows are well detected, and confusions with water and dark surfaces are overall reduced, but large shadows are not well detected in Ankara. We believe this could be improved by scaling the dataset to include more cities with tall buildings. If increasing the dataset is not sufficient, the receptive field of the network may have to be increased, or the encoder replaced by a vision transformer [33].

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